

INNOVATIVE APPROACHES TO DEVELOPING STUDENTS' TECHNICAL CREATIVITY

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ABSTRACT

This article analyzes the theoretical and methodological foundations of developing students' technical creativity, scholarly interpretations of creativity, factors shaping technical creative activity, and the importance of developing creative competencies within the technological education process..

In today's globalized world, preparing specialists with innovative thinking, creativity, and the ability to deeply understand technical processes has become a priority direction of the education system. Developing students' technical creativity is one of the essential tasks of modern vocational and technological education, requiring the cultivation of creative thinking, rationalization skills, and the ability to solve problem-based situations.

A. Aripdjanova, who extensively studied the concept of creativity from a pedagogical perspective, emphasizes that pedagogical creativity should be viewed through activity-based, environmental, personal, and problem-oriented dimensions [1]. G. Ibragimova defines creativity as "a set of skills related to inventiveness and the generation of new ideas," highlighting intuition, sensitivity, imagination, and reflection as its core components [2]. Sh. Pozilova interprets creativity as an activity aimed at producing original, non-standard ideas [3].

In philosophy, the term "creativity" originates from the Latin word *creo* — "to create," and is defined as the ability to find unconventional solutions to existing processes and problems [4]. In psychology, creativity is described as "the manifestation of an individual's creative potential, reflected in thinking, emotions, communication, and activity" [5].

Western scholars describe creativity from various perspectives. Taylor notes that by the mid-20th century, nearly 60 definitions of creativity had already been proposed [6]. Simpson explains creativity as "a departure from standard thinking and an orientation toward novelty" [7]. E. Gromova and V. Molyako identify seven qualities of a creative personality: originality, imagination, activity, purposefulness, sensitivity, precision, and emotional expressiveness [8].

A. Maslow divides creativity into two types: creativity based on innate talent, and creativity formed through self-actualization [9]. B. Johnson views creativity as a driving force that inspires individuals, suggesting that creative activity should be integrated into all aspects of education [10].

E. Torrance analyzes the creative process through four stages: preparation, incubation, illumination (insight), and evaluation [11]. C. Yarmoshenko describes creativity as “a creative force based on nontraditional thinking” [12].

M. Kholodnaya examines creativity in narrow and broad senses: narrowly — as the ability to perform various thinking operations; broadly — as intellectual activity aimed at generating new ideas and innovative solutions [13]. T. Edison considered creativity the product of hard work, constant inquiry, and persistence [14].

Psychologist E. Simpson defined creativity as “the ability to disrupt conventional patterns of thought and form unusual associations” [15]. Z.T. Nishanova, through her research, developed a model of creative thinking based on imagination, knowledge, skills, thought processes, motivation, and belief systems [16].

Studies on the relationship between creativity and intelligence show that although highly creative individuals often possess strong intellectual abilities, high intelligence alone does not guarantee creativity [17].

Developing students’ technical creativity requires independent inquiry, experimentation, the enhancement of technical thinking, and the formulation of original solutions in problem situations. Internet resources, contemporary scientific literature, technical design tasks, and hands-on practical sessions play a significant role in this process.

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